

Interference and Fermions and Bosons Part II

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 22, 2021

Two particle product type wavefunctions may be created so as to be symmetric (bosons) or antisymmetric (fermions) on then interchange of the identical particles. As a result, spatial density at a point does not change upon interchange. This approach, however, appears to be mathematical in nature. In Part I of this note, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ free particle momentum wavefunctions within a bound wavefunction $W(x)$ interfere and that full wavefunctions $W_n(x)$ in a linear combination also do the same. As a result, probability interference is ultimately linked to the physical mechanism associated with the periodic $\exp(ipx)$ wave behind the Pauli rule that fermions may not occupy the same quantum state. In this note, we try to extend this idea and argue that one does not simply exchange identical particles in the wavefunction as a mathematical procedure, but that actual exchange may occur in the probabilistic quantum mechanical case. We note that a time-independent treatment of scattering from a target already includes the idea of “negative” or out of phase interference within a wavefunction $W(x) = \exp(ikz) + f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r$ so as to remove some incoming flux as outgoing scattered flux now exists. We suggest that the “minus” sign used in the antisymmetric fermion wavefunction behaves in a similar manner. In (1), we argued that $W(x)W(x)$ in a bound state includes all possible $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ combinations and represented a product probability. In other words, a particle at x with p_1 $P(p_1/x)$ may be knocked into p_2 at x . Similarly, we argue that cross terms in a two particle fermion wavefunction represent flux $W^*b(x_1)Wa(x_1)W^*a(x_2)Wb(x_2)$ flowing from out of states as an interchange occurs. Main terms such as $W^*a(x_1)Wa(x_1)W^*b(x_2)Wb(x_2)$ represent the presence of particles in the a, b states. If $a=b$, the presence and flow probabilities cancel locally and there is a vanishing wavefunction i.e. the two fermions may not occupy the same state.

We argue that one should be able to describe the Pauli exclusion rule in this manner and note that Feynman (2) has used probability arguments in boson scattering to argue the boson enhancement factor. In other words, the mathematical argument of a symmetric wavefunction is not used, but a more physical argument is given.

Fermions and Bosons

In the case of two identical particles (which have product wavefunctions) with two energy levels a and b , one may insist that $P(x_1, x_2) = P(x_2, x_1)$. Given that $P(x_1, x_2)$ is obtained from the modulus squared of the wavefunction, one may create two linear combinations which satisfy this local constraint i.e.

$$W(x_1, x_2) \text{ fermion} = b \{ Wa(x_1)Wb(x_2) - Wa(x_2)Wb(x_1) \} \quad ((1a)) \quad b = \text{normalization factor}$$

$$W(x_1, x_2) \text{ boson} = b \{ Wa(x_1)Wb(x_2) + Wa(x_2)Wb(x_1) \} \quad ((1b))$$

This approach appears to be purely mathematical. It would be good to attempt to find a physical explanation behind the above result. (It is interesting to note that the symmetry in ((1)) is due to

a local constraint and the wavefunctions W_a and W_b (bound states) satisfy a local constraint as well i.e. local conservation of energy $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$ where $KE(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx] / W.$

Time-Independent Approach to Scattering

In (3), the scattering of a particle from a target is described in a purely time-independent manner i.e.

$$W = \exp(ikz) + f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r \quad ((2))$$

One may note that there is no classical time in such a probabilistic wave approach. In classical physics a particle leaves a source at t_1 , moves towards a target reaching the halfway point at t_2 , reaches the target at t_3 , scatters at t_4 and reaches the detector at t_5 . In quantum mechanics, one has a steady state probabilistic wave approach with interference occurring between $\exp(ikz)$ and the backward portion of $f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r$. Thus, the reduction in the incoming flux $\exp(ikz)$ due to particles being scattered out is due to interference. A probabilistic approach (quantum mechanics) is equivalent to a stream of particles entering the target zone, but yields a probability scenario for a single particle.

We argue that an antisymmetric fermion wavefunction becoming zero may be due to the same kind of interference with the minus sign indicating a loss of flux. We examine this idea further in the next section.

Fermion Antisymmetric Wavefunction and Loss of Flux.

Just as $f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r$ may yield a negative term canceling part of $\exp(ikz)$ (to indicate that some portion of the incoming particles are scattered), the -1 factor in an antisymmetric wavefunction may result in the cancellation of part of regular spatial density i.e.

$$\{W^*_a(x_1)W^*_b(x_2) - W^*_a(x_2)W^*_b(x_1)\} \{W_a(x_1)W_b(x_2) - W_a(x_2)W_b(x_1)\} \quad ((3))$$

$$= W^*_a(x_1)W_a(x_1)W^*_b(x_2)W_b(x_2) + W^*_a(x_2)W_a(x_2)W^*_b(x_1)W_b(x_1) \\ - W^*_a(x_1)W_b(x_1)W^*_b(x_2)W_a(x_2) - W^*_a(x_2)W_b(x_2)W^*_b(x_1)W_a(x_1)$$

The first two terms indicate regular spatial densities. In the first case state a is sampled at x_1 and state b at x_2 and in the second, a is sampled at x_2 and b at x_1 . The next two terms contain a minus factor which reduces this density.

For a single particle bound wavefunction spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ is equivalent to the sum of all $a(p_1) \exp(i p_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(i p_2 x)$. We argued in (2) that one might possibly interpret this as a particle with p_2 at x receiving a hit and becoming p_1 . In a classical statistical gas, the notion of $f(p)$ at any x is well-defined because there is a balance between forward and backward two body scattering reactions i.e. $e_1 + e_2 \rightarrow e_3 + e_4$ is balanced by $e_3 + e_4 \rightarrow e_1 + e_2$. In the quantum case, this is not so. Thus a p_2 may be knocked into p_1 without a p_1 being knocked into p_2 . Thus, one needs to consider product probabilities.

Here we argue that $W^*a(x_1)Wb(x_1)$ is of a similar nature, but applies to the full wavefunction. In other words a particle in state b is knocked into "a" and this carries an overall -1 to indicate a flux change at x_1 as opposed to $W^*a(x_1)Wa(x_1)$. As a result, one has a loss of probability spatial flux due to particle changes from state a to b combined with regular spatial densities. If $a=b$, these completely cancel at each x_1, x_2 pair. In other words, because of the physical interchange of identical particles from a to b and back combined with regular densities it is not possible to have two fermions in the same quantum state.

It may be noted that quantum mechanics represents a statistical picture which does not allow one to follow particles in time. For example, in a bound state one has both $-p$ and p at the same x . Even in the high energy limit these are not separated in time whereas a classical bound particle first moves in one direction (in a certain time interval) and then in the other direction in another time interval. In classical statistical mechanics, $f(p_1)$ is well defined at any instant in time because there is a balance of particles flowing out of the state p_1 (momentum) and into this state. In quantum mechanics (bound states) there is no classical time (just a cycling time) in the sense that one follows the particle in time and no well defined $f(p_1)$, although for the high energy case one almost has a p_1 and $-p_1$ at x_1 etc. Thus if a quantum system senses flux losses, as we argue seems to be the case for fermions, the statistical nature of the system and the loss of time tracking leads to a scenario in which there is a flux cancellation with spatial density if $a=b$. This only seems to make sense if the identical particles are continually changing from state a to b and vice versa. Given that the particles are identical, one would not see this except for the fact that two fermions cannot occupy the same quantum state.

The implications of the Pauli exclusion principle are enormous as is well known because they dictate that nucleons in a nucleus and electrons in an atom must occupy various increasing energy levels.

Feynman Description of Bosons

As a final point, we note that Feynman in his Lecture Notes (2) describes the boson enhancement factor in terms of physical boson scattering. In particular, he argues that a particle "a" may be scattered in direction 1 with wavefunction a_1 . To have particle "a" scatter in direction 1 and particle b in direction 2, one has the product wavefunction a_1b_2 . Particle 1 may scatter in direction 1 and "a" in direction 2. The probability is the amplitude squared and if one wishes to have two particles detected by detectors at 1 and 2 one has:

$$P = a_1a_1 b_2b_2 + a_2a_2 b_1b_1 \quad ((4))$$

If directions 1 and 2 are very close then $P = 2 aabb$ where $a_1=a_2=a$ and $b_1=b_2=b$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that for a two fermion system with energy states a and b, one has spatial density of the two particles in addition to flux loss associated with one particle leaving a and entering b while the other does the opposite. This is a statistical system with classical time removed, so one may think only in terms of probabilities (steady state flux). We

argue that this is similar to the time independent treatment of a particle scattering from a target. There is an incoming wavefunction $\exp(ikz)$ which interferes with a back portion of $f(\theta, \phi) \exp(ikr)/r$. The overall wavefunction is the sum of the two so the second term should bring in a “negative” sign to cancel part of $\exp(ikz)$. We argue that the negative sign in an antisymmetric fermion wavefunction is of the same nature. It represents flux moving out of states which cancels regular spatial density. In other words, $W^*_a(x_1)W_a(x_1)W^*_b(x_2)W_b(x_2) + W^*_a(x_2)W_a(x_2)W^*_b(x_1)W_b(x_1)$ represents flux at x_1 and x_2 respectively with the possibility of the two states brought in. At the same, one continuously has the two particles trying to leave their current state and go to the other which leads to flux loss i.e. $-W^*_a(x_1)W_b(x_1)W^*_b(x_2)W_a(x_2) - W^*_a(x_2)W_b(x_2)W^*_b(x_1)W_a(x_1)$. If $a=b$ one has zero which means two fermions may not be in the same state, i.e. the far-reaching Pauli principle. We try to describe this in terms of “physical” probability flows.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Joint Conditional Probability and Bound Quantum Density (preprint, zenodo, 2020)
2. https://www.feynmanlectures.caltech.edu/III_04.html
3. Shankar, R., Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum, 1988)